

¹Silver Nanoparticles Synthesized from *Aconitum Violaceum* Plant Leaf Extract Provide Sensitive and Selective Colorimetric Detection of Pb²⁺

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Abstract

This research introduces a cost-effective and straightforward colorimetric method for detecting Pb²⁺ ions. The method utilizes silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) that are synthesized from the extract of *Aconitum violaceum* leaves. Due to the presence of a substantial quantity of polyphenols in the extract, the AgNPs were effectively produced and analyzed by UV-vis spectroscopy, Fourier transforms infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The generated AgNPs were utilized as colorimetric probes for the detection of Pb²⁺. When Pb²⁺ was present, the AgNPs that were produced by biological means underwent a color transformation from yellowish to a deep red shade. This color shift was readily identifiable by UV-vis spectroscopy. The newly developed sensor exhibited excellent linearity in detecting Pb²⁺ ions within the concentration range of 0.8-2.4 M, with a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.982. The sensor's detection limit (LOD) was determined to be 0.1 M. Moreover, this sensing device exhibited a very specific response for the measurement of Pb²⁺

Keywords

Silver Nanoparticles; *Aconitum Violaceum* Leaf Extract; Lead; River Water.

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Accepted: 22 February 2024 / Published online: 24 February 2024

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Introduction

Our vapor-saturated environment contains a range of metal ions that come from both natural and anthropogenic sources. Some of these ions can be significantly or somewhat detrimental to human health [1]. Lead (Pb^{2+}) is the most detrimental metal ion due to its widespread presence in industrial pollution, making it a significant health hazard, especially in developing countries [2, 3]. Human skeletal structures and soft bodily substances can amass Pb^{2+} , resulting in harm to organs; when concentrations reach critical levels, it can lead to the demise of the organism [4]. Therefore, it is crucial to accurately quantify the concentration of these deleterious metal ions in aqueous environments. Furthermore, it is essential in most of these applications, including environmental monitoring, standardized water quality management, and polluted water recycling [5]. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) [6, 7], electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) [8, 9], and X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) are the most widely recognized methods for quantifying Pb^{2+} . Each of these methods necessitates expensive equipment, laborious sample preparation procedures, and a high level of expertise [10]. Conversely, colorimetric techniques utilizing metal nanoparticles are characterized by their ease of use, low cost, selectivity, and high sensitivity [11-16].

The colorimetric response of these sensors can be easily assessed either through visual observation or spectrophotometric analysis, without the need for complex equipment. Gold (Au) and silver (Ag) nanoparticles (NPs) are noble metals that have attracted significant attention for their colorimetric tests. These assays are popular due to their strong absorption and visual qualities, excellent stability, biocompatibility, and water solubility of Au and AgNPs [17-20]. Prior studies have utilized different ligand-functionalized gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) as colorimetric probes to detect Pb^{2+} ions [21-26]. Nevertheless, the fabrication of such sensors often requires the use of costly chemicals and very advanced methods of synthesis and modification. Unlike AuNPs, the development of a colorimetric assay for metal ion detection using AgNPs is both cost-effective and highly sensitive [27]. To detect Pb^{2+} using colorimetry, researchers have suggested using AgNPs that have been modified with suitable ligands [28-29]. Nevertheless, these approaches depend on the use of environmentally harmful and costly ligands.

The use of environmentally benign substances, such as plant extracts, is crucial for the synthesis of AgNPs using green methodologies. These methods are cost-effective, simple to adopt, and have minimal impact on the environment [30, 31]. The inclusion of hydroxyl, carboxyl, and hetero-aromatic rings in plant extracts that include multi-functional groups capable of interacting with metals presents a promising opportunity to create a highly efficient sensing technique for detecting dangerous metal ions in water-based solutions [32, 33].

The use of AgNPs derived from plant extracts has proven to be highly efficient as colorimetric probes for the detection of Pb^{2+} utilising the green chemistry technique [34, 35]. The primary drawbacks of these colorimetric sensors based on biosynthesized AgNPs are their limited selectivity and sensitivity, which can restrict their use in field monitoring applications. Therefore, there is still a need for the creation of a biosensor that can accurately detect Pb^{2+} ions with high selectivity and low detection limits [36-39]. We have developed a novel and precise colorimetric method for detecting Pb^{2+} ions using silver nanoparticles derived from the leaf extract of *Aconitum violaceum* plant. [40-42]. The proposed sensor

exhibited a colorimetric reaction that was both specific and highly responsive to Pb²⁺ ions. The test's color can be readily assessed either through visual examination or UV-vis absorption spectroscopy. Furthermore, we effectively utilized this colorimetric sensor to ascertain the presence of Pb²⁺ in actual water samples.

Materials and Methods

Fresh *Aconitum violaceum* leaves were collected from the Botanical garden of MDU Rohtak. In this experiment, highly pure (analytical grade) substances were used. Sigma Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany) provided silver nitrate (AgNO₃, 99.8%), lead nitrate Pb(NO₃)₂, and other metal salts. A specified amount of each metal salt was dissolved in deionized water to prepare the stock solution of each metal ion.

Preparation of plant extract

After being thoroughly rinsed with deionized water, the freshly picked leaves were allowed to dry in the shade and then milled into a powder. The plant extract was prepared by dissolving 20 g of powdered leaves in 100 mL of methanol. After four hours of continuous shaking, the mixture was filtered using Whatman filter paper. After filtering out the methanol, the mixture was left to dry at ambient temperature. Cold storage (4 degrees Celsius) was used for the dried extract [43].

Silver nanoparticles synthesis

A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5 grams of extract in 100 ml of deionized water. 8 ml of a 2 mM solution of silver nitrate was added to a 100 ml conical flask. Concentrated NaOH was used to adjust the pH to 11. Subsequently, a volume of 1.5 ml of extract was introduced to synthesize the AgNPs under ambient conditions. The solution underwent a chromatic transition from being colorless to acquiring a yellowish-brown hue after 8 hours of reaction time. In order to synthesize AgNPs using thermal means, a 100 ml conical flask was filled with 10 ml of a 2 mM silver nitrate solution in water, with the pH adjusted to 11. In order to prevent rapid evaporation, the flask was placed on a hot plate that was set to a temperature exceeding 80 degrees Celsius. While maintaining a continuous stirring speed of 800 revolutions per minute, 1.5 milliliters of extract were gradually added drop by drop to the solution as it reached its boiling point. The heaters were left running for an extra 6 minutes. During the progression of AgNPs production, the color of the solution changed to a yellowish tint. The produced AgNPs were used for colorimetric detection of Pb²⁺. AgNPs were synthesized using heat treatment and exhibited stability over a period of 9 months.[44].

Characterization techniques

To monitor the absorbance spectra of the synthesized AgNPs as well as the colorimetric detection of Pb²⁺, a double beam UV-vis spectrophotometer-1800 (Shimadzu, Japan) with cell (quartz) of 1 cm path length was employed [45, 48]. An X-ray diffractometer (Shimadzu, XRD-6000) was used to investigate the crystalline metallic character of AgNPs. The apparatus was configured with a Cu K α radiation source set to 50 kV. XRD diffraction data were analyzed under experimental conditions in the 2 θ range of 3° $\leq$ 2 θ $\leq$ 90°.

The AT-IR spectra were measured using a Bruker ATR Alpha spectrometer-I in the 400-4000 cm^{-1} range. For TEM measurements, a drop of colloidal solution was placed on a carbon-coated copper grid and dried at room temperature using a Hitachi H-8100 electron microscope (Tokyo, Japan).

Procedure for the colorimetric detection of Pb^{2+}

Before using the colorimetric detection method, the bio-functionalized AgNPs that were generated were diluted ten times with deionized water. To observe the colorimetric reaction, a 5 ml solution containing biofunctionalized AgNPs was diluted and then an appropriate amount of Pb^{2+} was added. The experiment involving interference was conducted by adding 50 M of each metal ion— Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Fe^{2+} , —to a 5 ml solution of AgNPs. Observation of the color change was possible both before and after the reaction was finished. The next step was to conduct the UV absorption test [49-51].

Sensor applications to real water samples

The water sample was acquired from the Tilyar lake in the district of Rohtak, Haryana, and was utilized as is, without being filtered. Pb^{2+} concentrations of 1.0, 2.5, 10, and 25 M were added to an 8 ml solution comprising river water (5 ml) (that does not contain similar in with same charge density) and AgNPs (6 ml) using a normal addition process. Following the completion of the reaction time, UV-vis measurements were performed [52-56].

Results and discussion

Synthesis of biosynthesized AgNPs

pH effect on the synthesis of AgNPs

The synthesis of AgNPs was investigated at various pH levels using *Aconitum violaceus* leaf extract. According to the UV-vis experiments (Fig. 1), pH 11 produced the highest, most intense surface plasmon resonance (SPR) absorption band at a significantly lower wavelength. According to the findings of this investigation, a relatively high basic medium was beneficial for the contents of the leaf extract to diminish and stabilize the AgNPs. As a result, pH 11 was chosen for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles.

Figure 1: UV-Vis absorption spectra of biosynthesized AgNPs at different pH

Effect of plant extract amount and reaction time

The influence of plant extract quantity on AgNPs production was studied in the range of 0.2 to 5.5 ml. The absorption intensity gradually rose as the amount of plant extract increased from 0.2 to 2 ml, as shown in Fig. 2(A). This shows the solution's high concentration of AgNPs. The absorption intensity gradually reduced as the concentration was increased from 1.5 to 5 ml. This means that with 1.5 ml of extract, the reduction and stabilization of all Ag⁺ ions are nearly complete. The decrease in absorption intensity with amounts more than 1.5 ml may be attributed to an excess of extract remaining in the solution after complete AgNPs reduction. As a result, 1.5 ml was sufficient for the full reduction of AgNPs.

Figure 2 A: Effect of Aconitum violaceum extracts amount on the absorption intensity of AgNPs; B: Effect of Aconitum violaceum extracts reaction time on the absorption intensity of AgNPs

We also investigated the reaction time for the production and stabilization of AgNPs at different time intervals. As demonstrated in Fig. 2(B), the intensity of the SPR band of AgNPs increased with response time up to about 8 hours. The absorption intensity remained nearly constant as the reaction time was increased further. This implies that the synthesis of AgNPs takes 8 hours to complete the reaction process. The major disadvantages of plant-based AgNPs synthesis are that it takes a long time to complete the reaction process and exhibits a large and less intense SPR band in the UV-vis region. To solve these issues, we heated the reaction mixture over 110°C for 8 minutes. In comparison to the nanoparticles generated at ambient temperature, the SPR peak of the AgNPs solution grew, became narrower, and emerged at a lower wavelength (400 nm) after heating (Fig. 3). Similarly, the colour of the AgNPs solution immediately changed to bright yellow rather than dark brown, as shown in the inset of Fig. 3. The intense character of the band along its emergence at a lower wavelength suggests the creation of AgNPs with tighter size distributions, which is similar to chemical reduction techniques.

Figure 3: UV-vis absorption spectra showing the effect of heat treatment on the synthesis of AgNPs.

This could be significant for colorimetric detection applications that require high sensitivity. We also doubled the heating period from 6 to 18 minutes, but there was no significant change in peak intensity. This result demonstrated that the long 8-hour reaction time for the production of AgNPs utilizing plant extract was finished in just 6 minutes after heat treatment. As a result, 6 minutes was chosen as the ideal heating time for the preparation of AgNPs.

Characterization of biosynthesized AgNPs

FT-IR analysis

The FT-IR investigation is useful for investigating the presence of biomolecules in plant extracts and observing probable interactions of biomolecules with AgNP surfaces. The IR spectra of the plant leaf extract (Fig. 4) revealed a broadband centred at around 3381.5 cm^{-1} , which is related to the stretching frequency of the OH group. Similarly, the peaks observed at 1600 , 1350 , and 1077 cm^{-1} could be attributed to C=C ring stretching, COH or CH₃ bending, and CO stretching modes, respectively. A minor peak at 1689 cm^{-1} was also found, which corresponds to the stretching frequency of the C=O group. The presence of these groups in the IR spectrum suggests that the plant extract has a high concentration of polyphenols, primarily catechins-type compounds. In comparison, the peaks in the IR spectra of biosynthesized AgNPs are displaced and have lower intensities, indicating that the biomolecules in the extract may have an affinity to interact with AgNPs, primarily via their oxygen functions, which operate as reducing and capping agents. These findings are consistent with the earlier reports [57].

Figure 4: FT-IR spectra of the plant leaf extract and biosynthesized AgNPs

XRD Analysis

To establish the crystalline character of the biosynthesized AgNPs, an XRD investigation was done using the X-ray diffraction method. The XRD pattern, as shown in Fig. 5, explains the number of Bragg reflections at two θ values of 34.42°, 39°, 58.2°, and 73.6°, which correspond to the (110), (200), (220), and (310) lattice plane sets [58]. The manifestation of these planes is based on the face-centered cubic structure of silver. The XRD patterns revealed that the silver nanoparticles made using the current green approach were crystalline in form. The amorphous and crystalline organic elements may be responsible for the additional tiny peaks at 32°, 66°, and 78° [59].

Figure 5: XRD pattern of AgNPs synthesized from *Aconitum violaceum* plant leaf extract

TEM analysis

A TEM analysis was performed to approximate the shape and size distribution of the as-prepared AgNPs. The TEM picture of the synthesized AgNPs is given in Figure 6. The production of AgNPs was confirmed by Fig. 6A. The particles were mostly circular and had a diameter of less than 18 nm.

Figure 6A: TEM images of biosynthesized AgNPs, in the absence of Pb^{2+}
6B: TEM images of biosynthesized AgNPs, in the absence of Pb^{2+}

Colorimetric assay for Pb^{2+}

Because the plant extract contains a considerable number of polyphenols, primarily catechins compounds, as determined by FT-IR measurement, the bio-functionalized AgNPs can be employed as colorimetric probes for Pb^{2+} detection. Because it contains a catechol moiety, catechin forms stable complexes with Pb^{2+} , according to the literature. Yan and colleagues [] employed catechin-stabilized Au nanoparticles for the detection of Pb^{2+} in environmental samples based on this complexation. Similarly, Liuji et al [2004] employed tea catechin to prevent cells from oxidative damage caused by Pb^{2+} poisoning. Based on these findings, the usage of AgNPs stabilized by catechins polyphenolic substances found in *Aconitum voiloeum* leaf extract as a colorimetric probe for the detection of Pb^{2+} was investigated [60]. To investigate the potential interaction between Pb^{2+} ions and biosynthesized AgNPs, 100 M Pb^{2+} was added to the solution containing the biosynthesized AgNPs. When Pb^{2+} was added, the colour of the AgNPs solution immediately changed from yellow to red[61]. UV-vis spectroscopy was used to monitor this colour change, which revealed a remarkable spectral variation, namely the appearance of a new absorption peak at 520 nm and a decrease in absorption intensity at 404 nm, as shown in Fig. 7 (photographic image in inset shows the corresponding colour transformation). This research demonstrates that Pb^{2+} ions can interact with AgNPs.

This is mostly due to Pb^{2+} 's ability to combine with the electron donor's hydroxyl groups of catechins polyphenols present on the surfaces of AgNPs to create Pb-catechin AgNPs complexes. As a result of this complexation, the AgNPs quickly aggregated in the solution, as demonstrated by TEM examination in Fig. 6(B).

Figure 7: UV-vis spectra of biosynthesized AgNPs showing the colorimetric sensing property of Pb^{2+} (100 μM).

Biosynthesized AgNPs' Sensitivity

The proposed biosynthesized sensor's sensitivity to Pb^{2+} was tested. As Pb^{2+} concentration increased from 0.3 to 3 M, the classic UV-vis absorption peaks of AgNPs gradually diminished at 400 nm, while new absorption bands developed at 510 nm, as shown in Fig. 8. Similarly, when the spectrum changes, the color of the AgNPs solutions changes from bright yellow to orangish red. Based on these spectral changes, the absorption ratios (A_{520}/A_{404}) were calculated and displayed as a function of Pb^{2+} concentrations. Over time, a linear calibration plot was obtained [62].

Figure 8: UV-vis absorption peaks of AgNPs

Sensitivity to Pb²⁺

The selectivity of the suggested biosynthesized AgNPs for Pb²⁺ detection was tested in the presence of various interfering metal ions or Pb²⁺, as well as in the coexistence of interfering ions and Pb²⁺. Except for Pb²⁺, none of the other metal ions examined changed the color or absorption ratio of the AgNPs solution (Fig. 9). There was also no significant difference in the absorption ratio responses of AgNPs solutions containing only Pb²⁺ and mixtures of all metal ions including Pb²⁺, indicating that the presence of all other metal ions did not affect the detection of Pb²⁺. The presence of catechol moiety in catechin molecules on the surfaces of AgNPs, which have strong complexing capacity towards Pb²⁺, could be linked to the selective response of the generated AgNPs [63, 64].

Figure 9: Graph represent the absorbance in responses of biosynthesized AgNPs for different interfering metal ions

Application in real-world water samples

The developed sensor's practical usefulness for Pb²⁺ measurement in river water samples was evaluated using a typical addition process [65-67]. Pb²⁺ was spiked into a solution containing river water and AgNPs at various known quantities for this purpose. The findings demonstrated that good recoveries ranging from 97 to 110%. This illustrates the potential of the proposed combination of the system with AgNPs for easy discrimination and quantification of Pb²⁺ from the aqueous medium. These findings suggested that the new sensing device may be used to analyze Pb²⁺ in real-world water samples.

Conclusions

In this study, we devised a simple colorimetric approach for detecting Pb²⁺ using AgNPs assisted by *Aconitum violaceum* leaf extract. Because of the presence of catechin polyphenols on the surfaces of AgNPs, Pb²⁺ was selectively recognized in the solution by the bio-functionalized AgNPs by creating a

catechinPb²⁺catechin complex. This complexation led AgNPs in the solution to aggregate, resulting in a color change from yellow to red. This unique methodology has several distinct advantages over previously reported colorimetric systems, including being simple, selective, low cost, rapid, and free of harmful substances. Furthermore, the measured LOD is equivalent to the described chemical reduction methods for Pb²⁺ detection. The suggested sensing technique could be used to detect Pb²⁺ in river water samples without the need for a laborious pre-treatment step.

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